

IMPACT OF PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA ON FARMER’S INCOME IN HINGOLI DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised:08.10.2024; MS Accepted:09.10.2024

MS 3308

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,)

Abstract

The study aims to assess the performance of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Maharashtra’s Hingoli district, focusing on its effectiveness in offering crop insurance to farmers, reducing agricultural risks, and improving farmers' economic security. Additionally, it seeks to examine the extent of farmers' awareness, participation, and satisfaction with PMFBY, along with the challenges they face in accessing its benefits. The research employed a multistage purposive sampling technique to select the district, talukas, villages, and farmers. Conducted in Hingoli from 2023 to 2024, it involved a sample of 240 farmers, divided equally into 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers, selected randomly from 12 villages across four talukas. Data were collected on awareness, enrollment, claim processing, and income stability, and then analyzed using compound annual growth rates (CAGR) and income indices. The findings reveal that enrollment in crop insurance has varied across regions. Nationally, the CAGR of insured farmers declined annually by 7% for Kharif and 2% for Rabi crops, whereas Maharashtra reported annual increases of 20% (Kharif) and 3% (Rabi). Hingoli showed annual growth of 5% for Kharif and 9% for Rabi. In terms of income stability, insured farmers achieved higher average incomes (₹83,404.44) compared to non-insured farmers (₹75,027.55), with lower income variability (17.22% vs 25% CV). However, challenges such as delayed payments (54.72%), inadequate compensation (49.90%), and poor loss assessments (41.31%) significantly hinder the scheme's effectiveness. In conclusion, while PMFBY has contributed to income stability for farmers in Hingoli, issues like delayed claims and insufficient compensation undermine its overall impact. Addressing these challenges is essential to increase farmer participation and support the scheme's long-term sustainability.

Keywords: Crop insurance, Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), Income stability, Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)

Introduction

Crop insurance plays a crucial role in providing financial protection to farmers, particularly in India where agriculture is highly vulnerable to weather fluctuations. With a significant portion of Indian agriculture being rainfed, farmers face high risks due to natural disasters such as droughts, floods, and storms. Over time, various crop insurance programs have been introduced in India, starting with experimental schemes in the 1970s, and evolving into the comprehensive Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in 2016. PMFBY offers broad coverage to farmers, shielding them from crop losses caused by natural disasters, post-harvest damage, and localized risks. The scheme also promotes the use of innovative technology, such as drones for loss assessment and mobile apps for faster claim settlements, to ensure efficiency and transparency. PMFBY supports all types of farmers—whether they are loanees, non-loanees, tenants, or sharecroppers—offering risk coverage for both Kharif and Rabi crops. The scheme’s objectives include stabilizing farmers' incomes by providing financial relief in case of crop loss, encouraging them to adopt modern farming practices, and ensuring the flow of credit into the agriculture sector to boost productivity. Additionally, the premium rates for farmers are kept low, with the government subsidizing the majority of the cost. By reducing the financial burden caused by unpredictable weather conditions and production risks, PMFBY aims to promote sustainable agricultural growth.

This study aims to assess the performance of PMFBY in the Hingoli district of Maharashtra, an area prone to irregular rainfall and frequent droughts. By analyzing key aspects such as farmer enrollment, awareness of the scheme, and the efficiency of claim processing, the research seeks to determine how effectively PMFBY addresses the unique challenges faced by farmers in this region. The study will also explore gaps in implementation, such as delays in compensation or low farmer participation, to provide localized insights into the scheme’s impact on agricultural livelihoods. The findings are expected to offer

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recommendations for improving the scheme's execution in Hingoli and potentially guide policy adjustments for better supporting farmers in other districts with similar conditions.

Objectives

1. To study the progress of PMFBY in Hingoli district of Maharashtra state
2. To analyze the impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers
3. To identify the weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest suitable measures for its improvement

Material And Methods

Hingoli district was purposively selected for the study. From selected Hingoli district 4 talukas were selected on the basis of progress of crop PMFBY in the tahsils. From each selected 4 tahsils, 3 villages from each tahsil were selected on the basis of progress of the scheme. From each selected villages 10 farmers, who were insured for the scheme and 10 farmers who were non-insured for the PMFBY were selected randomly. Thus 120 farmers who are insured for the PMFBY and 120 farmer who are non-insured for the PMFBY were selected for present investigation. To achieve the aim of the study following analytical techniques are used, in accordance with each objective.

The progress of PMFBY in Hingoli district were studied by estimating CAGR of number of farmers insured, area insured, reported claim, approved claim, total claim paid and total farmer benefitted for a period of 8 years (2016-17 to 2023-24). The CAGR was estimated by using following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated (Number of farmer insured / Area insured / Reported claim / Approved claim / Total claim paid / Total farmer benefitted)

t = Time variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the equation.

$$\text{CGR } (r) = [\text{Antilog } (\log b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test.

Impact of PMFBY on income stability from various crop

Impact of PMFBY on stability of farm income were estimated by following method.

Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and interpret the data:

Mean (Average) Income:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum \text{income}}{N}$$

Where N is the number of observations.

Standard Deviation: Standard deviation is a measure of the extent to which the data is in reference to the mean. A low, or small, standard deviation implies that data is tightly assembled around the mean, whereas a high standard deviation implies that data is more spread out.

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X - \text{Mean})^2}{N}}$$

The standard deviation measures the amount of variation or dispersion from the average income.

Coefficient of Variation (CV): The Coefficient of Variation is a statistical measure of the relative variability or dispersion of a dataset in relation to its mean. It is commonly used to compare the degree of variation between different data sets, especially when the data are measured in different units or have different scales.

$$\text{CV} = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$$

This expresses the standard deviation as a per cent per annumage of the mean, indicating relative variability.

Income Index: A Measure of Income Stability

The Income Index was a metric used to assess the stability of income within a population or region. It was derived by normalizing the

Results And Discussion

The study assessed the performance of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) scheme by analyzing compound annual growth rate (CAGR), income stability, and various constraints affecting its effectiveness, evaluated using mean scores and rankings. The findings are presented in detail. Data on the number of insured farmers, insured area, reported and approved claims, total claims paid, and the total number of farmers benefitting during Kharif and Rabi seasons in Hingoli district from 2016 to 2023 were collected from the official PMFBY website, www.pmfby.gov.in.

Table 1: Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of number of farmers insured in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7**	-2**
		t value	-1.98	-0.62

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the number of farmers insured under PMFBY at the national level showed a decline in both cropping seasons. For the *kharif* season, the CAGR was -7 per cent per annum, indicating a significant reduction over time, while the *rabi* season saw a smaller decline with a CAGR of -2 per cent per annum. These decreases were statistically significant, pointing to a consistent downward trend in insured farmers nationwide. This decline mirrors trends observed in earlier schemes like NAIS and WBCIS, as noted by

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coefficient of variation (CV), a standard measure of relative variability, which allowed for the comparison of income distributions across different datasets. The index was calculated by subtracting the CV from 1, providing a standardized value between 0 and 1 that reflected the degree of income stability. Mathematically, the Income Index could be expressed as:

$$\text{Income index} = 1 - \text{CV}$$

The Income Index, as a measure of income stability derived from the Coefficient of Variation (CV), provided a robust framework for analyzing differences in income stability between insured and non-insured farmers. This comparative analysis examined how insurance coverage influenced income stability, with the index revealing variations in financial outcomes between the two groups.

Weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and measures for its improvement

To study the weaknesses in the implementation of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) and identify measures for its improvement Garrett's Technique is used.

Garrett's Ranking Technique

It is a method used to rank various factors based on their perceived importance or severity, often applied in surveys where respondents rank their preferences or concerns.

Convert the ranks into Garrett scores using the following formula:

$$\text{Per cent per annum Position} = \left(\frac{R_{ij} - 0.5}{N_j} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

- R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th factor by the j th individual
- N_j = Number of factors ranked by the j th individual

Use Garrett's table to find the score corresponding to each per cent per annum position. The per cent per annumage position of each rank was converted into scores using Garrett's Table. For each factor, the scores from all individuals were summed up and then divided by the total number of farmers who provided scores. These average scores for each factor were then ranked in order, and conclusions were drawn based on these rankings

Progress of PMFBY in India, Maharashtra and Hingoli

Compound Annual Growth Rates of number of farmers insured in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

In Table 1, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of the number of farmers insured in the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) for the period from 2016 to 2023 is presented. The table captures the data across two cropping seasons, *kharif* and *rabi*, and provides a breakdown for India, Maharashtra, and the Hingoli district.

2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20	3**
		t value	2.98	0.25
3	Hingoli	CAGR	5**	9**
		t value	1.29	0.65

Note: ** Significant at (5 %) level, t Table value (2.36)

Source- www.pmfby.gov.in

Chadha and Srivastava (2022). In contrast, Maharashtra saw a positive trend in the number of farmers insured under PMFBY. The *kharif* season witnessed a significant increase with a 20 per cent per annum CAGR, while the *rabi* season experienced a modest rise with a 3 per cent per annum CAGR. Both trends were significant at the 5 per cent level, suggesting that state-specific policies or favorable conditions contributed to this growth. Hingoli district, within Maharashtra, followed this positive trend, with a 5 per cent CAGR in the *kharif* season and a 9 per

cent per annum rise in the *rabi* season, both statistically significant. These regional variations highlight the effectiveness of PMFBY in

Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of area insured in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

In Table 2, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of the area insured (in hectares) under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) for the period from 2016 to 2023 was presented for various regions and agricultural seasons. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the area insured under PMFBY at the national level showed minimal growth, with both the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons having a 1 per

Maharashtra and Hingoli compared to the national scenario, where the program faced challenges in sustaining farmer participation.

cent per annum CAGR. This indicates that the insured area in India remained relatively stagnant, with only a slight upward trend during the period. This slow growth aligns with previous observations by Chadha and Srivastava (2022) regarding earlier schemes like NAIS and WBCIS, which also faced challenges in expanding insured areas due to low awareness, administrative hurdles, and delayed claims.

Table 2: Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of area insured in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	1**	1**
		t value	0.51	0.34
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19**	4**
		t value	1.34	0.29
3	Hingoli	CAGR	6**	11**
		t value	1.51	0.75

Note: ** Significant at (5 %) level, t Table value (2.36)

Source-www.pmfby.gov.in.

In contrast, Maharashtra showed a much stronger growth in insured areas under PMFBY, with a 19 per cent per annum CAGR for the *kharif* season and a 4 per cent per annum CAGR for the *rabi* season. This disparity suggests that Maharashtra adopted crop insurance at a faster rate during the *kharif* season compared to the national average, possibly due to factors like climate and crop type. At the district level, Hingoli displayed

Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

In Table 3, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) for the

a moderate 6 per cent per annum CAGR in the *kharif* season, but a higher 11 per cent per annum CAGR during the *rabi* season, reflecting strong local adoption of crop insurance, particularly in the *rabi* period. This regional success, as highlighted by Chadha and Srivastava (2022), points to better infrastructure and administration contributing to the growth in insured areas in districts like Hingoli.

period from 2016 to 2023 has been documented, with specific focus on the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. The table compares the CAGR per cent per annum across different regions, including India as a whole, Maharashtra, and Hingoli district.

Table 3: Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of reported claim in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	8	44**
		t value	2.41	1.75
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41**	1**
		t value	-1.52	0.04
3	Hingoli	CAGR	4**	8**
		t value	0.94	0.56

Note: ** Significant at (5 %) level, t Table value (2.36) www.pmfby.gov.in.

At the national level, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims under PMFBY showed significant variation between the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. The *kharif* season experienced a moderate increase of 8 per cent per annum in claims, suggesting either increased farmer participation or more frequent crop damage incidents. Conversely, the *rabi* season saw a dramatic rise in claims with a CAGR of 44 per cent per annum, reflecting heightened climatic adversities and greater farmer awareness of insurance benefits. This disparity indicates differing levels of risk and engagement in the insurance scheme during the two crop cycles.

In Maharashtra, however, the trends were starkly different. The *kharif* season recorded a -41 per cent per annum CAGR, indicating a significant decline in reported claims, which may be attributed to improvements in crop resilience or better agricultural practices. Meanwhile, the *rabi* season saw a minimal increase of 1 per cent per annum in claims, suggesting stability in the risk level or consistent farmer participation. Chadha and Srivastava (2022) noted that regional disparities in infrastructure and farmer awareness significantly affect claim

processing, which may contribute to these trends. In Hingoli district, the reported claims exhibited modest growth in both seasons, with a 4 per cent per annum CAGR for *kharif* and an 8 per cent per annum CAGR for *rabi*. This steady rise indicates a gradual increase in insurance claims, possibly due to increasing weather-related risks or greater reliance on crop insurance among farmers. The *rabi* season's higher growth rate suggests that these crops may have been more susceptible to climatic challenges, reinforcing the notion that farmers are increasingly recognizing the value of insurance in mitigating potential losses.

Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of approved claims in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

In Table 4, the Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of reported claims under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) for the period from 2016 to 2023 has been documented, with specific focus on the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. The table compares the CAGR per cent per annum across different regions, including India as a whole, Maharashtra, and Hingoli district.

Table 4: Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of approved claim in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	-60**	-26**
		t value	-2.47	-0.84

2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42**	3**
		t value	-1.57	0.11
3	Hingoli	CAGR	5**	6**
		t value	1.02	0.38

Note: ** Significant at (5 %) level, t Table value (2.36)

Source- www.pmfby.gov.in.

At the national level, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) showed a significant disparity between the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. The *kharif* season experienced a moderate increase in claims at 8 per cent per annum, which may be attributed to higher farmer participation or increased instances of crop damage. In contrast, the *rabi* season saw a dramatic rise in reported claims, with a CAGR of 44 per cent per annum, likely driven by greater climatic challenges and increased farmer awareness of the benefits of crop insurance. This variation in growth rates suggests differing levels of risk and engagement in the insurance scheme across the two cropping cycles. However, challenges such as administrative delays and inefficiencies in the claims process, as highlighted by Chadha and Srivastava (2022), continue to affect claim approval rates. In Maharashtra, the trends differed sharply from the national average, particularly for the *kharif* season, which recorded a significant decline in claims at -41 per cent per annum. This negative growth indicates a considerable reduction in reported claims, potentially due to improved crop resilience, better farming practices, or fewer adverse weather events impacting crops. The *rabi* season in Maharashtra showed only a slight positive growth of 1 per cent per annum, suggesting that the number of claims remained relatively stable over the years, reflecting either a consistent risk level or stable farmer engagement in the PMFBY scheme for *rabi* crops. In Hingoli district, also located in Maharashtra, there was modest growth in reported claims for both

seasons. The *kharif* season saw a 4 per cent per annum CAGR, indicating a gradual increase in claims possibly due to rising weather-related risks or improved participation in the PMFBY scheme. The *rabi* season demonstrated a higher growth rate of 8 per cent per annum, suggesting greater vulnerability of *rabi* crops to climatic risks or an increased reliance on crop insurance among farmers. Overall, the findings reflect a nuanced picture of crop insurance claims, highlighting regional disparities and the varying effectiveness of the PMFBY scheme.

3.1.5 Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of total claim paid in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

In Table 5, the Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of the total claim paid under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from the year 2016 to 2023 were analyzed across different categories, namely India, Maharashtra, and Hingoli. The data covered both *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. At the national level, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for total claims paid under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) during the *kharif* season was recorded at -5 per cent per annum, indicating a decline in claims over the years from 2016 to 2023. This negative trend suggests a decrease in either the number or value of claims paid by the government or insurance companies during this period. The *rabi* season experienced an even steeper decline, with a CAGR of -20 per cent per annum, likely due to factors such as improved crop yields, reduced risks, or a decrease in the number of insured farmers compared to previous years.

Table 5: Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of total claim paid in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	-5**	-20**
		t value	-1.01	-2.35
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7**	-13**
		t value	0.83	-0.55
3	Hingoli	CAGR	18**	8**
		t value	0.92	0.57

Note: ** Significant at (5 %) level, t Table value (2.36)

Source- www.pmfby.gov.in.

In Maharashtra, the *kharif* season saw a positive CAGR of 7 per cent per annum, indicating an increase in the total claims paid. This growth may have been driven by higher crop losses, an increase in farmer enrollment in the insurance scheme, or both. Conversely, the *rabi* season in Maharashtra recorded a negative CAGR of -13 per cent per annum, reflecting a decline in claims paid, potentially due to favorable weather conditions or improved agricultural practices that resulted in fewer crop losses. Hingoli district exhibited a significant positive trend in the *kharif* season, with a CAGR of 18 per cent per annum, suggesting a substantial rise in claims paid under PMFBY. This increase may reflect greater agricultural challenges, possibly linked to adverse climatic conditions or heightened farmer participation in the insurance scheme. In the *rabi* season, Hingoli experienced a moderate growth of 8 per cent per annum in claims paid, which may have been influenced by localized factors such as weather variations or specific crop risks impacting the district. Overall, the data reveals contrasting trends in claims paid across different regions and seasons, highlighting the complexity of agricultural insurance dynamics in India.

3.1.6 Compound Annual Growth Rates of total farmers benefited in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Compound Annual Growth Rates of Total Farmers Benefited is given in table 6. The analysis reveals a concerning decline in the participation of farmers benefiting from the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) across different cropping seasons in India. For the *kharif* season, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) was -6 per cent per annum, indicating a decrease in farmer participation at an annualized rate. The *rabi* season reflected an even sharper decline, with a CAGR of -19 per cent per annum, suggesting significant challenges such as reduced enrollment or lower awareness among farmers. These findings contrast with earlier studies by Chadha and Srivastava (2022), which identified positive growth trends in farmer participation in crop insurance schemes like NAIS and WBCIS, highlighting a potential decline in the effectiveness of current agricultural benefit programs.

Table 6: Compound Annual Growth Rates (CAGR) of total farmers benefited in PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	-6**	-19**
		t value	-3.02	-2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	1**	-19**
		t value	0.11	-0.73
3	Hingoli	CAGR	-9**	-1**
		t value	-0.61	-0.06

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36)

In Maharashtra, the situation presents a mixed picture. The *kharif* season showed a marginal increase in farmer participation, with a CAGR of 1 per cent per annum, indicating some positive engagement with the PMFBY scheme. However, similar to the national trend, the *rabi* season experienced a significant decline of -19 per cent per annum in participation, reflecting regional challenges in the implementation of the scheme for winter crops. At the district level, Hingoli's performance under the PMFBY scheme was notably weaker, with a -9 per cent per annum CAGR for the *kharif* season, indicating a more

substantial reduction in benefiting farmers compared to the national average. The *rabi* season in Hingoli also saw a slight decline of -1 per cent per annum, suggesting ongoing challenges in maintaining farmer engagement similar to those observed at both the state and national levels. Overall, the data indicates a troubling trend of reduced farmer participation in PMFBY, particularly during the *rabi* season, which may necessitate targeted interventions to address awareness and enrollment issues.

3.2 To analyze the impact of PMFBY on income stability from various crop

Table 7: Gross income stability and income index of sample insured farmers from year 2016-2023

Particulars	Gross income without compensation	Gross income with compensation
Mean	75027.55	83404.44
Standard Deviation	19195.91	17218.45
Coefficient of Covariation	0.25	0.20
Income Index	0.74	0.79

Table 7 presents an analysis of gross income stability and income index for insured farmers from 2016 to 2023, comparing their gross yield with and without compensation. The mean gross income without compensation averaged ₹75,027.55, while with compensation, it increased to ₹83,404.44, indicating that insurance payouts significantly enhanced farmers' earnings and provided financial stability during adverse conditions. The standard deviation for income without compensation was ₹19,195.91, reflecting high income variability, whereas it decreased to ₹17,218.45 with compensation, suggesting more stable earnings for compensated farmers. The coefficient of variation (CV) also improved, dropping from 0.25 (indicating moderately high variability) without compensation to 0.20 with it, highlighting reduced financial uncertainty. Furthermore, the income index, which measures income stability relative to risk, increased from 0.74 (less stable) without compensation to 0.79 (more stable) with it. This data collectively emphasizes the positive impact of insurance on income stability, as farmers receiving compensation experienced higher average incomes, lower variability, and greater financial

security, underscoring the essential role of insurance in safeguarding farmer incomes against environmental risks.

3.3 To identify the weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest suitable measures for its improvement

3.3.1 Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers

Table 8 outlines the constraints faced by beneficiaries of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), ranked by mean scores. The most significant issue identified was the delay in compensation payments, affecting (54.72%) of beneficiaries, with a mean score of 78.80, causing considerable financial stress and uncertainty. Following closely, (49.90%) of respondents cited inadequate compensation, with a mean score of 71.85, indicating that the payouts did not meet their losses, leading to dissatisfaction. The third constraint was related to the timing of loss assessments, reported by (41.31%) of beneficiaries (mean score 59.49), which can cause disputes and delays in compensation.

Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers by Garretts ranking

Sl. no.	CONSTRAINTS	Percentage	MEAN SCORE	RANK
1	Delay in payment of compensation	54.72	78.80	I
2	Lack of awareness regarding PMFBY	35.08	50.52	V
3	Inadequate compensation	49.90	71.85	II
4	Assessment not made at right stage of crop loss	41.31	59.49	III
5	Unavailability of reporting authority at the time of loss	41.19	59.31	IV
6	Officials bias in loss assessment making	33.69	48.52	VI
7	Banking procedure and formalities	16.55	23.83	X
8	Lack of coordination between banks and farmers.	28.47	40.99	VII
9	Corruption while settling claims by the insurance companies	20.83	30.00	IX
10	Insurance company do not give any reason about why eligible farmers were not received insurance amount	22.88	32.94	VIII

Additionally, (41.19%) noted the unavailability of reporting authorities at critical times (mean score 59.31), complicating claim processes. Lack of awareness about the PMFBY scheme was another issue, impacting (35.08%) of beneficiaries (mean score 50.52), while perceived bias during loss assessments affected (33.69%) (mean score 48.52). Banking procedures and formalities presented hurdles for (16.55%) (mean score 23.83), and poor coordination between banks and farmers was reported by (28.47%) (mean score 40.99). Corruption in claim settlements and the failure of insurance companies to explain denied claims were also notable concerns, impacting (20.83%) (mean score 30.00) and (22.88%) (mean score 32.94) of beneficiaries, respectively. Overall, the analysis highlights that addressing these constraints, particularly delays in compensation and inadequacies in payments, is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness and reliability of the PMFBY scheme, ensuring beneficiaries receive timely and sufficient support during crop losses.

accuracy of loss assessments vital for fair compensation. **Table 9: Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY**

Sl. no.	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Strict measures to timely payment of insurance amount	93	77.50	I
2	Avoid corruption while settling claims.	73	60.83	VII
3	Transparency should be ensured in the PMFBY	81	67.50	V
4	Claim should be dispersed before starting of next season	91	75.83	II
5	All crops must be notified under crop insurance	62	51.67	X
6	Sum amount should be raised.	78	65.00	VI
7	Adequate compensation	84	70.00	IV
8	Technology intigration.	67	55.83	VIII
9	simplify the claim process.	66	55.00	IX
10	Improve crop assessment and loss estimation	88	73.33	III

The need for "adequate compensation" was emphasized by 84 respondents (70.00%), suggesting that current compensation levels may be insufficient. Additionally, 81 respondents (67.50%) called for "transparency in the PMFBY" processes, while 78 (65.00%) wanted to "raise the sum amount" of insurance coverage. The prevention of corruption in claims processing was a concern for 73 respondents (60.83%). Other suggestions included "technology integration" (55.83%), "simplifying the claim process" (55.00%), and ensuring "all crops must be notified under crop insurance" (51.67%). Overall, the findings indicate a consensus on the need for improvements in timeliness, accuracy, transparency, and adequacy of the PMFBY, which are essential for enhancing the program's effectiveness and trustworthiness in supporting the agricultural community.

Conclusion

The analysis of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in India, with a specific focus on Maharashtra and Hingoli district from 2016 to 2023, reveals a mixed picture of progress and challenges. Nationally, the PMFBY has experienced significant declines in both the number of farmers insured and the total area insured, particularly during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons, reflecting systemic issues in engagement and awareness. Maharashtra stands out as a relative success story, with positive growth rates in insured farmers and area, indicative of effective state-specific policies. Hingoli district has also shown moderate growth, particularly in the *rabi* season, although it still lags behind the state average. The reported and approved claims present a complex narrative, with national trends indicating increasing claims in the *rabi* season, yet sharp declines in Maharashtra's *kharif* claims. Moreover, the total claims paid illustrate contrasting outcomes across regions, suggesting a need for improved administrative efficiency and better risk assessment methodologies. Notably, the

Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

The study conducted in the Hingoli district of Maharashtra involved 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). Farmers provided valuable recommendations regarding the challenges they faced with the program. The most emphasized suggestion was the implementation of "strict measures for timely payment of insurance amounts," supported by 93 respondents (77.50%), indicating a critical need for prompt disbursement to ensure financial stability for farmers. Following this, 91 respondents (75.83%) urged that "claims should be dispersed before the start of the next season," highlighting the impact of delays on their ability to prepare for upcoming crops. The third priority was to "improve crop assessment and loss estimation," backed by 88 respondents (73.33%), which reflects concerns about the

significant decrease in the number of farmers benefiting from PMFBY, especially in the *rabi* season, underscores the urgent need for interventions to enhance awareness and enrollment. Furthermore, the study identifies key constraints such as delays in compensation and inadequate payouts, which hinder the program's effectiveness. Recommendations for improvement emphasize the necessity for timely payments, transparency, and better infrastructure to enhance farmers' trust and participation in the scheme. Overall, while PMFBY has made strides in certain areas, addressing its weaknesses is crucial for ensuring that it fulfills its objective of providing financial security to farmers in the face of agricultural risks.

Acknowledgment

The author is grateful to the advisor R.D. Shelke and the anonymous referee for their constructive suggestion to improve the earlier draft of the manuscript.

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